

Flowering on 1-10 Nov indicates that most varieties have critical photoperiod longer (12-12.5 h) than those of Thai, Burmese, and Vietnamese varieties. For

this reason, most Bangladesh photoperiod-sensitive varieties flower too early if planted in Thailand and in similar latitudes. On the other hand, the

introduced photoperiod-sensitive varieties flower later than Bangladesh varieties because their critical photoperiod is shorter. □

Grain yield and duration of ratoon rice varieties

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To evaluate ratoon performance, we measured grain yield and duration of 10 short- and medium-duration rice varieties during 1984-85 at ACRI.

The main as well as ratoon crop received 100-22-41.5 kg NPK/ha. Immediately after rice harvest, ratoon stubbles were cleaned. Irrigation was given from day 3 onwards. All P and K plus half of N was applied 7 d after cutting. The balance of N was applied in 2 splits on day 25 (maximum tillering) and day 35 (panicle initiation).

Ratoon crop yields varied from 0.43 to 2.20 t/ha (see table). Bhavani's high

Grain yield and duration of ratoon rice. Madurai, India, 1984-85.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)			Crop duration (d)	
	Main planted crop	Ratoon	Ratoon yield compared with planted crop yield (%)	Planted crop	Ratoon
Bhavani	2.5	2.2	86.6	128	78
Ponni	1.7	0.4	27.2	138	88
Puduvai Ponni	2.4	0.8	31.5	138	66
IR20	3.0	0.9	30.7	128	77
ACM8	0.8	0.7	80.0	120	67
ACM9	3.6	1.2	34.6	104	81
ACM10	2.9	1.6	54.3	104	81
CO43	2.6	0.7	25.9	135	69
CO44	2.0	0.9	46.6	120	81
MDU2	2.6	0.5	17.9	138	77
LSD (P=0.05)	0.5				

^aYellowing disease reduced yields.

yield of 2.2 t/ha was 86.6% of main crop yield. Ratoon crop durations varied from 69 to 81 d. Bhavani's field duration was 128 d in the main crop and 78 d in

ratoon crop. Analysis showed no significant correlation between ratoon crop grain yield and duration. □

Hybrid rice in rainfed environments

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Two hybrids (IR46830A/IR9761-19-1R and IR54752A/IR46R) and their parents were dry seeded (75 kg/ha) and grown under strictly rainfed conditions in lowland and upland fields of IRRI in 1987 wet season. IR46, one of the parents, was the check variety. Urea (90 kg N/ha) was topdressed on 17 Sep. Water deficit occurred 45 to 60 d after seeding (DAS) with a maximum stress of 69 kPa soil moisture tension at 20 cm soil depth and 5 kPa at 60 cm.

The table shows the performance of the F₁ hybrids and their parents under rainfed conditions. Hybrid IR46830A/IR9761-19-1R yielded

Yield and yield components of 2 F₁ hybrid rices and their parents under rainfed environments. IRRI, 1987.

Entry	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	100-grain weight (g)	Filled grains (%)	Harvest index
<i>Lowland site</i>					
IR46830A/IR9761-19-1R (F ₁)	3.2	1118	1.90	62.62	0.30
IR9761-19-1	0.7	788	1.28	57.05	0.18
IR46830	2.4	986	1.78	62.19	0.30
IR54752A/IR46R (F ₁)	2.2	716	2.13	56.67	0.20
IR46	2.3	926	2.03	72.09	0.28
IR54752	1.7	574	2.30	62.73	0.20
LSD (0.05)	0.4	320	0.20	22.50	0.06
<i>Upland site</i>					
IR46830A/IR9761-19-1R (F ₁)	1.0	970	1.93	64.28	0.30
IR9761-19-1	0.6	794	1.73	42.75	0.30
IR46830	0.5	910	1.65	46.60	0.23
IR54752A/IR46R (F ₁)	0.8	522	2.15	69.80	0.20
IR46	0.6	492	1.90	69.20	0.23
IR54752	0.8	490	2.20	62.50	0.25
LSD (0.05)	0.3	220	0.18	14.66	0.08

highest with 105% midparent heterosis for the lowland trial and 78% for the upland trial. Hybrid IR54752A/IR46R,

exhibited only 7% and 8% midparent heterosis in the 2 trials and yielded as much as did IR46.